

BREASTFEEDING PRACTICES AMONG WORKING CLASS WOMEN IN OGBOMOSO NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT SECRETARIAT, OYO STATE

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Abstract: Exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) remains one of the most effective strategies for improving infant survival and promoting maternal health. Despite widespread awareness of its benefits, the practice of EBF remains low, particularly among working-class women who face a range of occupational, physical, and socio-cultural barriers. In Nigeria, where infant morbidity and mortality are prevalent, understanding the dynamics of EBF among employed mothers is essential for informing public health interventions and policy reform. This study aimed to assess the knowledge, breastfeeding performance, and challenges associated with exclusive breastfeeding among working-class women in Ogbomoso North Local Government Area, Oyo State. The objective was to evaluate the level of awareness and practice of EBF, identify barriers influencing its implementation, and explore the role of occupation and institutional support in shaping breastfeeding behaviors. A descriptive cross-sectional design was used, and data were collected from 177 working mothers via a structured questionnaire that incorporated the Breastfeeding Performance Index (BPI). The instrument assessed socio-demographic factors, knowledge of EBF, breastfeeding practices, and related challenges. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 22, applying both descriptive and inferential statistics, including chi-square tests to examine relationships among variables. The results showed that 78.5% of the respondents were aware of EBF, and 76.8% correctly identified its six-month duration. A high proportion (83.6%) demonstrated good breastfeeding performance, although knowledge did not significantly predict performance ($p = 0.889$). However, breastfeeding performance was significantly associated with actual EBF practice ($p = 0.002$) and with mothers' occupations ($p < 0.001$). Major challenges reported included inadequate maternity leave, sore nipples, insufficient milk production, and cultural pressure to introduce artificial feeds. The researchers conclude that while knowledge of EBF is high among working mothers, practice is constrained by structural and cultural barriers. We recommend extending maternity leave to six months, implementing workplace breastfeeding support, and strengthening community education efforts to promote sustainable exclusive breastfeeding practices.

1. Introduction

Breastfeeding is one of the most effective public health interventions for improving maternal

and child health. Exclusive breastfeeding, defined as feeding an infant only breast milk for the first six months of life except for prescribed

medicines, vitamins, and mineral supplements, provides adequate nutrition, strengthens immunity, supports growth and cognitive development, and promotes mother-infant bonding (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021; Kayode et al., 2023). It also reduces infant morbidity and mortality by protecting against common childhood illnesses such as diarrhoea and respiratory infections (Onyinyechukwu et al., 2021). For mothers, breastfeeding is associated with reduced risks of breast and ovarian cancers, improved postpartum recovery, and long-term health benefits (WHO, 2021).

Despite these benefits, exclusive breastfeeding remains suboptimal globally and in Nigeria. Although awareness may be high, a substantial gap still exists between knowledge and practice, with exclusive breastfeeding rates varying widely across settings (Onwuka, 2022; Apará, 2024). Recent evidence shows that women's employment status, workplace conditions, and family support strongly influence exclusive breastfeeding practice (Atibinye et al., 2022; Ibekwe et al., 2022). In particular, working-class women face difficulty sustaining exclusive breastfeeding because of short maternity leave, inflexible work schedules, stress, fatigue, insufficient milk supply, and lack of breastfeeding-friendly workplace support (Onwuka, 2022; Ibekwe et al., 2022).

In Nigeria, breastfeeding is widely practiced, but exclusive breastfeeding is still poorly sustained, especially among employed mothers. This low practice contributes to preventable infant health problems, including infections, poor growth, malnutrition, and later-life metabolic risks (Onyinyechukwu et al., 2021; Adebayo et al., 2020). Although several studies have examined knowledge and attitudes toward

exclusive breastfeeding, fewer have focused on the practical challenges faced by working-class women in local government settings, such as the Ogbomoso North Local Government Secretariat in Oyo State (Adebayo et al., 2020; Onwuka, 2022). This creates a local evidence gap that limits the design of targeted interventions.

This study, therefore, examines the knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding, breastfeeding performance, and the challenges experienced by working-class women in Ogbomoso North Local Government Secretariat. The findings are expected to inform workplace policies, health education, and maternal support strategies that can improve exclusive breastfeeding practice and strengthen maternal and child health outcomes (Kayode et al., 2023; WHO, 2021).

2. Literature Review

Exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) for the first six months, as recommended by the World Health Organization, is widely recognized as the optimal infant feeding practice, with continued breastfeeding alongside complementary foods up to two years or beyond (Onwuka, 2022). It offers important health benefits for infants, including immunity against infections, improved brain development, better cognitive performance, and reduced risk of obesity, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes later in life. For mothers, EBF supports birth spacing, mother-child bonding, and lowers the risk of type 2 diabetes, ovarian cancer, and breast cancer (Onwuka, 2022; Shekara and Shekara, 2023).

2.1 Knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding among working-class women

Studies suggest that knowledge of EBF is influenced by education, age, income, and access to information. Ogbonna (2020)

reported that women with higher income and education levels were less likely to breastfeed, while younger women were less informed and less likely to adhere to EBF practices, showing the need for early sensitization of girls and adolescents. Lartey (2022) emphasized that counseling and quality education can improve nutritional knowledge, attitudes, and breastfeeding practices, although poor support from health workers may limit this effect. In Ibadan, Leshi and Amoo (2023) found that 94% of married women and 50.4% of unmarried women in Purdah were knowledgeable about EBF. Similarly, Abekah-Nkrumah et al. (2020) found that most respondents understood EBF as feeding a baby only breast milk for the first six months, with antenatal clinics, nurses, midwives, family members, and the internet serving as major sources of information.

2.2 Breastfeeding performance index among working-class women

The breastfeeding performance index (BPI) is used to summarize optimal breastfeeding practices and assess how well mothers adhere to recommended feeding patterns (Oot, 2020). It is important because breastfeeding reduces child mortality, improves intelligence outcomes, and lowers the risk of obesity and diabetes later in life (Sankar, 2021; Bosnjak, 2020). Although exclusive breastfeeding is possible for nearly all mothers, global data show that many infants are still not exclusively breastfed for the recommended six months (WHO, 2021; UNICEF, 2022; Victora, 2022). In Ethiopia, for example, only 59% of infants under six months were exclusively breastfed in 2019, while some infants were given water, non-milk liquids, or other milks before six months (EPHI, 2019). Monge-Montero et al. (2020) also reported that mixed feeding remains common

globally, and Anderson et al. (2021) showed that mixed feeding still carries risks, even though it may be better than no breastfeeding at all. Senarath (2022) noted that the higher the BPI, the greater the likely benefit from breastfeeding, making it a useful tool for assessing interventions.

2.3 Exclusive breastfeeding practices among working-class women

EBF practice remains low, especially among employed women and mothers who introduce complementary foods early (WHO, 2021). Cultural beliefs, personal experience, and support networks influence practice among Yoruba women, where EBF is often viewed positively but not always sustained (Faleye, 2019). Spancer (2022) observed that mothers' control over breastfeeding within their socio-cultural environment is limited, and that breastfeeding may be experienced as stressful, exhausting, or satisfying depending on personal circumstances. In industrial settings, long work hours and short maternity leave often reduce the ability to breastfeed on demand, leading some mothers to rely on infant formula or other foods (Myers, 2020). Salami (2021) further noted that inadequate milk flow, poor nutrition, lack of family support, and cultural beliefs, including fears that breastfeeding may cause breast sagging, can discourage EBF.

2.4. Challenges of exclusive breastfeeding among working-class women

Several barriers affect EBF among working women. Short maternity leave prevents mothers from establishing stable breastfeeding routines and forces early return to work, which disrupts feeding patterns (Abidemi, 2024). Lack of institutional support, including private spaces for expressing and storing breast milk, flexible

schedules, and breastfeeding-friendly policies, makes it difficult to maintain EBF at work (Abekah-Nkrumah et al., 2020). Work-family imbalance, poor self-care, fatigue, and inadequate nutrition can reduce milk supply and weaken breastfeeding success. Late closing hours and shift work also increase mother-child separation and reduce opportunities for on-demand feeding, which further lowers EBF practice (Otubah, 2024).

The Theory of Planned Behavior explains breastfeeding practice well because it links behavior to attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). In this framework, a woman is more likely to practice exclusive breastfeeding if she believes it is beneficial, feels supported by important people around her, and thinks she can successfully carry it out. The theory also highlights the role of knowledge, self-efficacy, environmental conditions, and experience in shaping behavior. This helps explain why some working-class women may recognize the importance of EBF yet still fail to practice it consistently.

The theoretical framework shows that exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) is influenced by mothers' intentions, which are shaped by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. In simple terms, mothers are more likely to practice EBF when they believe its benefits outweigh its difficulties, when they receive support from spouses, family, and friends, and when they feel capable of sustaining the practice despite work or personal demands. The framework, therefore, links knowledge, social support, and self-confidence to actual breastfeeding behavior.

Evidence from previous studies shows that knowledge of EBF is generally high among

many working women, but actual practice is often lower than expected. Kayode et al. (2020) found that 98.1% of working women in Osogbo had good knowledge of EBF, yet only 66.8% had good practice. Most respondents correctly understood EBF as breast milk only, knew that breastfeeding should begin immediately after delivery, and recognized the value of colostrum and exclusive feeding for six months. However, some women still introduced complementary feeding before the recommended time, and work-related factors such as maternity leave duration, breastfeeding breaks, crèche availability, and family support influenced practice.

Similarly, Diji, Bam, and Owusu (2016) reported that 95% of mothers attending child welfare clinics in Ghana had good knowledge of EBF, but major challenges included the belief that breast milk alone was insufficient, short maternity leave, and socio-cultural pressure to introduce water and artificial feeds. This shows that knowledge alone does not guarantee good practice when social and occupational barriers remain.

In Ethiopia, Gessesse et al. (2022) found poor breastfeeding performance overall, with a low breastfeeding performance index in 79.05% of mothers with infants aged 0–6 months. Many mothers did not initiate breastfeeding on time, some practiced pre-lacteal feeding, and only about two-thirds breastfed in the previous 24 hours. The study showed that breastfeeding performance remains weak in many settings, even where breastfeeding is widely recognized as important.

Adebayo et al. (2020) also found that among working mothers attending the antenatal clinic in Lagos University Teaching Hospital, 62.4% had good knowledge and 59.8% had good

practice of EBF. The major challenges identified were the mother's health condition, the baby's health condition, cracked or sore nipples, inadequate milk production, and the work schedule. The study further showed significant relationships between knowledge and practice, and between educational qualification and practice.

2.4 Overall pattern

Across the studies, a clear pattern emerges: mothers often know the importance of exclusive breastfeeding, but their ability to practice it is affected by workplace conditions, family support, cultural beliefs, health problems, and maternity leave length. The literature therefore suggests that improving EBF requires more than education alone; it also requires practical support at home and in the workplace. This is especially relevant for working-class women, whose breastfeeding behavior is shaped by both personal intention and external constraints.

3. Methodology

3.1 Study Design: This study adopted a cross-sectional descriptive research design to examine exclusive breastfeeding practice and the challenges experienced by working-class women in Ogbomoso North Local Government Secretariat. A cross-sectional descriptive design is suitable because it allows the researcher to collect data from respondents at a single point in time and describe existing conditions as they relate to breastfeeding knowledge, practice, and barriers. The study site is situated in Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Southwestern Nigeria, a major city with a diverse population and significant occupational activity, making it an appropriate setting for investigating breastfeeding practices among employed mothers.

3.2 Study Population

The population for the study consisted of working mothers in the Ogbomoso North Local Government Secretariat. These are women who are actively engaged in work or business and are likely to face the practical demands that may influence their ability to exclusively breastfeed their infants. The focus on working mothers is important because employment-related factors such as work schedules, maternity leave, and workplace support often affect breastfeeding behavior. By concentrating on this population, the study aims to generate evidence that is directly relevant to maternal and child health promotion in the local government area.

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling

The sample size was determined using Yamane's formula, which is commonly applied when estimating a sample from a known population. Using the stated population of 320 working mothers and a precision level of 0.05, the calculated sample size is approximately 177. The study included only those working-class mothers who gave consent to participate. Women who are on leave or too ill to participate were excluded from the study because they may not be able to provide complete or reliable responses.

3.4 Instruments for Data Collection

Two main instruments were used in data collection. The first instrument was a researcher-structured questionnaire on Knowledge and Challenges of Exclusive Breastfeeding (QKCEB). This questionnaire was developed after reviewing relevant literature and adapting ideas from previous studies. It consisted of three sections. Section A contains 9 items on the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents such as age, marital status, occupation, and educational

background. Section B has 7 items that assess knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding, including understanding of the meaning, duration, and benefits of exclusive breastfeeding. Section C contains 8 items that assess the challenges respondents face in practicing exclusive breastfeeding, such as work-related stress, inadequate support, breast problems, and maternity leave limitations.

For knowledge questions, each correct response was awarded a point, and cumulative scores were used to classify knowledge as either "Low" or "High." The second one is the Breastfeeding Performance Index (BPI) Scoring System, which is a standardized tool used to assess breastfeeding performance among infants aged 0–6 months. This index contains seven components, and the scoring ranges from 0 to 7, with higher scores indicating better breastfeeding performance. The BPI is useful because it captures multiple dimensions of breastfeeding behavior rather than relying on a single question or general impression.

3.5 Validity and Reliability

The instruments were subjected to both face validity and content validity to ensure that they are appropriate for the study. A test-retest method reliability test was adopted. The Cronbach's alpha was 0.813 and 0.882.

3.6 Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher obtained ethical clearance from Bowen University Teaching Hospital (BUTH). After that, a formal letter of introduction was secured from the Dean of the Faculty of Nursing Science at Bowen University to request permission to conduct the study among the working-class women in Ogbomosho North Local Government Secretariat.

The questionnaires were administered in a way that minimized stress and inconvenience to

respondents. The researcher used face-to-face administration to improve clarity, encourage participation, and increase the return rate of the questionnaires. This method also allowed immediate clarification of any unclear items, which helps improve the accuracy of the responses. The questionnaires were collected on the same day they are completed to reduce the risk of loss or incomplete retrieval. Data collection lasted for two weeks.

3.7 Data Analysis

The data collected for the study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize respondents' socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding, breastfeeding practice, and reported challenges.

Chi-square was used to determine whether significant associations existed between the variables of interest, such as knowledge and breastfeeding performance, or job-related factors and exclusive breastfeeding practice. P values less than 0.05 were considered significant. All analyses were done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles were strictly observed throughout the study. Participants were informed about the purpose, objectives, and procedures of the research before participating. They were assured that their participation is voluntary, and no form of coercion will be used. Each respondent will have the right to decline or withdraw from the study at any stage without any negative consequence.

The researcher ensured the privacy and confidentiality of all information provided by

respondents. The data were handled in a way that protects the identity of the mothers and prevents unauthorized access. In addition, the researcher ensured that the study would not cause harm to participants and that all respondents would be treated equally and respectfully. Informed consent was obtained

before any questionnaire was administered, and participants were given an adequate explanation of the study’s purpose to support informed decision-making.

4. Finding

4.1 Findings

Table 1: Knowledge of Exclusive Breastfeeding among Working-Class Women in Ogbomoso North Local Government Secretariat

		NUMBER	PERCENTAGE %
Have you heard about exclusive breastfeeding?	Yes	139	78.5
	No	38	21.5
Have you ever practiced exclusive breastfeeding before?	Yes	134	75.7
	No	43	24.3
What is exclusive breastfeeding?	Breastfeeding with formula	10	5.6
	Breastfeeding with breast milk only	124	70.1
	Breastfeeding with solid foods	29	16.4
	All of the above	14	7.9
When is breastfeeding initiated?	Immediately after delivery	153	86.4
	Two weeks after delivery	7	4.0
	Two days after delivery	14	7.9
	B&C	3	1.7
How often is baby exclusively breastfed?	On demand and every hours	2133	75.1
	Every 3 hours	21	11.9
	Every 2 hours	15	8.5
	Every 4 hours	8	4.5
How long does exclusive breastfeeding lasts?	2-4 months	16	9.0
	4months	15	8.5
	6 months	136	76.8
	12 months	10	5.6

Source: Research Data, 2024

The findings in Table 1 indicated that respondents had a strong understanding of exclusive breastfeeding. Most had heard of EBF

(78.5%), had practiced it before (75.7%), correctly defined it as breast milk only (70.1%), knew that breastfeeding should begin immediately after delivery (86.4%), and

identified six months as the correct duration (76.8%). Most also recognized feeding on

demand or every two hours as appropriate practice (75.1%).

Figure 1: Knowledge level of the respondents. Source: Research Data, 2024

The majority were classified as having high knowledge (Figure 1).

4.1.2 Breastfeeding Performance of Working-Class Women

Table 2: Breastfeeding Performance of Working-Class Women in Ogbomosho North Local Government Secretariat

		NUMBER	PERCENTAGE %	Score
Early breastfeeding initiation	Yes	163	92.1	1
	No	14	7.9	0
Pre- lacteal feeds	No	163	92.1	1
	Yes	14	7.9	0
Bottle feeding	No	153	86.4	1
	Yes	24	13.6	0
Exclusive Breastfeeding	Yes	159	89.8	1
	No	18	10.2	0
Receiving liquids	No	163	92.1	1
	Yes	14	7.9	0
	No	158	89.3	1

Receiving formula or any other milk	Yes	19	10.7	0
Receiving solids	No	161	91.0	1
	Yes	16	9.0	0

Source: Research Data, 2024

Breastfeeding performance was generally high among the women studied. Using the Breastfeeding Performance Index, most respondents showed adherence to recommended

practices such as early initiation of breastfeeding, avoidance of pre-lacteal feeding, exclusive breastfeeding, and not introducing liquids, formula, or solids too early. (Table 2)

Fig. 2: Exclusive Breastfeeding Performance Level of the respondents. Source: Research Data, 2024

In total, 83.6% were classified as having high breastfeeding performance, while 16.4% had low performance (Fig. 2).

4.1.3 Challenges of Exclusive Breastfeeding among Working-Class Women

Table 3: Challenges of Exclusive Breastfeeding among Working-Class Women in Ogbomoso North Local Government Secretariat

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Difficulty combining work and breastfeeding	70 (39.5%)	49 (27.7%)	41 (23.2%)	17 (9.6%)
Number of children	71 (40.1%)	43 (24.3%)	44 (24.9%)	19 (10.7%)
Shyness when breastfeeding in public	72 (40.7%)	50 (28.2%)	32 (18.1%)	23 (13.0%)
Socio- cultural pressure to introduce water and artificial feeds	19 (10.7%)	90 (50.8%)	43 (24.3%)	25 (14.1%)
Inadequate milk production	14 (7.9%)	92 (52.0%)	46 (26.0%)	25 (14.1%)
Cracked, sore nipples	9 (5.1%)	142 (80.2%)	22 (12.4%)	4 (2.3%)
Inadequate maternity leave	134 (75.7%)	18 (10.2%)	21 (11.9%)	4 (2.3%)

Source: Research Data, 2024

Table 3 shows that the major challenges to exclusive breastfeeding were structural, physical, and socio-cultural. The most frequently reported barrier was inadequate maternity leave (75.7% Strongly Agreed), followed by cracked or sore nipples (80.2% Agreed), inadequate milk production (52.0% Agreed), pressure to introduce non-breast milk feeds (50.8% Agreed),

shyness about breastfeeding in public (40.7% Strongly Agreed), the number of children (40.1% Strongly Agreed) and difficulty combining work with breastfeeding (39.5% Strongly Agreed). These results show that even when knowledge and practice are high, mothers still face important barriers that can affect sustained exclusive breastfeeding.

4.1.4 Hypotheses Testing

Table 4: Chi-square association between knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding and exclusive breastfeeding performance

	Exclusive Breastfeeding	
	Low exclusive breastfeeding performance	High exclusive breastfeeding performance
Knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding	5	23
High Knowledge	25	124

Chi-square .019, df = 1, Sig=.889. Source: Research Data, 2024

Table 4 shows that there was no statistically significant association between the knowledge of

exclusive breastfeeding and the exclusive breastfeeding performance, $p = 0.889$.

Table 5: Chi-square association between knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding and breastfeeding performance index

	Practice of exclusive breastfeeding	
	Yes	No
Breastfeeding Performance Index	16	14
Low exclusive breastfeeding performance		
High exclusive breastfeeding performance	118	29

Chi-square 9.831, df= 1, sig.= .002. Source: Research Data, 2024

Table 5 shows a significant association between the breastfeeding performance index and exclusive breastfeeding practice, $p = 0.002$.

Table 6: Association between Mothers' Job Specification and Exclusive Breastfeeding Practice among Working-Class Women in Ogbomoso North Local Government Secretariat

Occupation		Have you ever practiced exclusive breastfeeding before	
		Yes	No
Administrative Role		12	7
	Finance and accounts	38	14

Health Dept	7	0
Educational Dept	6	0
Works and engineering	19	16
Agriculture and natural resources	18	0
Clerk and support staff	29	1
Legal unit	2	3
Information and public relations	2	1
Internal Audit Dept	1	1

Chi-square=31.986, *df*= 9, *sig.* = <0.001. Source: Research Data, 2024

Table 6 shows job specification was significantly associated with exclusive breastfeeding practice, $p < 0.001$.

4.2 Discussions

The study showed that working-class women in Ogbomoso North Local Government Secretariat generally had good knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding and relatively high breastfeeding performance (Figures 1 and 2), but they still encountered significant obstacles that may hinder the continued practice of exclusive breastfeeding (Table 3). These findings imply that awareness alone is not enough; practical, workplace, and socio-cultural support are also necessary for successful exclusive breastfeeding. The finding that most respondents had heard of exclusive breastfeeding and correctly understood its meaning, timing, and duration is consistent with earlier studies that reported high awareness among mothers. Kayode et al. (2020) found similarly high knowledge among working-class women in Osogbo, where most respondents correctly defined exclusive breastfeeding and knew that it should begin immediately after delivery and continue for six months. Likewise, Diji, Bam, and Owusu (2016) reported that most mothers had good knowledge of exclusive

breastfeeding, showing that breastfeeding education is widely available in many settings. The dominance of hospitals as the major source of information in this study also agrees with evidence that antenatal and postnatal health services remain the main channel for breastfeeding education in Nigeria.

The high breastfeeding performance reported in this study is encouraging and suggests that many women were able to translate knowledge into practice. This aligns with findings from Kayode et al. (2020), who observed that a majority of working women in Osogbo practiced exclusive breastfeeding appropriately, although a substantial minority still fell short of the recommended standard. However, the result contrasts with studies that reported poorer breastfeeding performance in other settings, such as Gessese et al. (2022), who found a high prevalence of low breastfeeding performance among mothers of infants aged 0–6 months in Ethiopia. This difference may reflect stronger local support, better awareness, or differences in workplace and social environment.

The major challenges identified in this study, especially inadequate maternity leave, sore nipples, low milk production, socio-cultural pressure, and difficulty combining work with breastfeeding, are consistent with the wider literature. Diji et al. (2016) similarly found that short maternity leave, the belief that breast milk alone was insufficient, and pressure to introduce water or artificial feeds were major barriers. A recent Nigerian qualitative study also confirmed that breastfeeding is shaped not only by mothers but by family elders, community beliefs, and the wider service environment, showing that social support systems strongly affect breastfeeding continuation (Costenbader et al., 2025). The findings from this study also agree with work from Oyo State showing that duration of maternity leave, breastfeeding breaks at work, crèche availability, and husband/family support are key factors influencing exclusive breastfeeding among working mothers (Olowolafe, Olaoye and Joel-Medewase, 2026). Although the study found strong knowledge and relatively high performance, there was no significant association between knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding and exclusive breastfeeding practice (Table 4), this and the presence of significant barriers shows that knowledge alone does not automatically translate into optimal breastfeeding practice (Moret-Tatay et al., 2025; Sabo et al., 2023). Mothers may understand the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding but still struggle because of work pressure, physical discomfort, or family expectations (Abekah-Nkrumah et al., 2020; Oputa-Uzoukwu and Joseph, 2026). This finding is in line with broader Nigerian evidence showing

that exclusive breastfeeding is shaped by a combination of personal, household, community, and service-level factors rather than information alone (Kayode et al., 2023). The result, therefore, supports the need for combined interventions that include education, maternity protection, breastfeeding breaks, and family support (Flax et al., 2022; Oputa-Uzoukwu and Joseph, 2026; WHO, 2022).

This finding shows a clear and statistically significant link between having practiced exclusive breastfeeding and achieving higher breastfeeding performance (Table 5). In practical terms, respondents with prior exclusive breastfeeding experience were more likely to score well on the Breastfeeding Performance Index, suggesting that real-life feeding experience strengthens optimal breastfeeding behaviors (Gessese et al., 2022). This result can be discussed as evidence that breastfeeding performance is not only a knowledge issue but also a practice-related behavior shaped by experience. Mothers who have actually practiced exclusive breastfeeding may better understand feeding schedules, infant cues, and the discipline needed to avoid supplemental feeds, which can raise their BPI scores (Gessese et al., 2022). The finding also aligns with the broader literature showing that breastfeeding performance indices are useful for capturing the quality of breastfeeding practices and their relationship with maternal or child outcomes (Gessesse et al., 2022).

The significant association between job specification and exclusive breastfeeding practice suggests that occupational demands and workplace flexibility play a major role in whether

women can sustain EBF. This is consistent with findings from previous Nigerian studies showing that women with more flexible or supportive work environments are more likely to breastfeed exclusively, while those in demanding jobs often struggle to maintain the practice (Kayode et al., 2020; Olowolafe et al., 2026). The result supports the view that breastfeeding should not be treated only as a maternal issue, but as a workplace and public health issue requiring institutional support (PAHO/WHO, 2021; Tomori, 2023; WHO, 2021).

4.3 Implications

The findings have important implications for nursing and medical practice, health education, and workplace policy. Health workers should continue to provide breastfeeding counseling during antenatal and postnatal care, but they should also address practical barriers such as milk expression, sore nipple management, and coping with work demands. Employers and policymakers should strengthen maternity leave provisions, provide breastfeeding-friendly spaces, and allow flexible breaks to help working mothers sustain exclusive breastfeeding. Community education should also target family members and cultural influencers so that breastfeeding support extends beyond the health facility.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

The study concludes that although awareness of exclusive breastfeeding is high among working women, actual practice is limited by workplace, physical, and socio-cultural barriers. It also shows that occupation influences breastfeeding behavior, with women in more supportive jobs

more likely to practice exclusive breastfeeding. The findings reinforce the idea that exclusive breastfeeding is not determined by knowledge alone; it depends on a supportive environment at home, at work, and within the health system.

5.2 Recommendations

The study recommends extending maternity leave to six months, creating breastfeeding-friendly workplaces, integrating breastfeeding education into routine nursing care, promoting community campaigns to reduce cultural barriers, and using the Breastfeeding Performance Index in maternal health monitoring. Together, these measures could improve exclusive breastfeeding practice and support better maternal and child health outcomes.

5.3 Strengths and Limitations of the Study

Overall, the methodology is appropriate for achieving the study objectives because it combines a structured descriptive design, validated and reliable instruments, and suitable statistical procedures. By focusing on working mothers in Ogbomoso North Local Government Secretariat, the study is positioned to generate locally relevant findings on exclusive breastfeeding knowledge, practice, and challenges. The results are likely to provide practical evidence that can support maternal health education, workplace policy improvement, and breastfeeding promotion efforts in the area.

The study was limited by its focus on one local government area, which reduces how widely the findings can be generalized. It also relied on self-reported responses, which may introduce recall or social desirability bias. Because the design was

cross-sectional, the study could not establish cause-and-effect relationships or track changes over time. In addition, some occupational groups had very small numbers, limiting subgroup comparisons, and the scoring system may not have captured the full depth of knowledge and challenges.

Declarations

Human Ethics and Consent to Participate

The study was conducted in line with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Approval to conduct the study was given by the Ethics and Research Committee of Bowen University Teaching Hospital, Ogbomosho. Approval was also obtained from Ogbomosho North Local Government, Oyo State head of personnel. Verbal consent was obtained from the respondents. The researchers ensured that the respondents were well-informed before soliciting their consent. The following ethical principles were also considered:

Respondent's autonomy: Only respondents who gave consent were assessed. In addition, they were allowed to withdraw from their studies at any time they wished, without any consequence.

Confidentiality: Confidentiality of information exchanged with the study groups remains with the respondents and the researchers.

Study Hazards: No hazard resulted from the study because the researcher only elicited information from the respondents.

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Consent for publication

Not applicable

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

Declaration of conflict of interests

The authors declared no potential conflict of interest.

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Authors' contributions

All authors were involved in the conception of the research idea, design, and implementation of the project. Data collection and data entry were done by MEO. CCHO and MEO carried out the statistical analysis and interpretation of data. CCHO wrote the manuscript and arranged to journal specifications. All authors read and approved the final manuscripts and this submission.

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